

ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF DESIGN

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ANNOTATION: This article describes the methodology used in design-based assessment of students and provides examples of how students can learn and implement it. The article shows the design and analysis methodology of each subject through selected examples from mathematics, English, physics, history, and biology.

A math example can help students learn algebra and graph analysis. The English example allows students to improve their speaking, analytical, and writing skills through novel analysis and attention to detail. A physics example shows how students use a methodology to select a sample from concrete, analyze it, and explain the relationships between cells and forces.

KEY WORDS: formative assessment, tests, quizzes, oral questions, diagnostic assessment, summative assessment.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that today there are changes in all areas of our society, rapid development to meet world standards. In particular, in the education system, on December 24, 2021, the head of our state signed two historic decisions on granting independence in financial, academic and organizational management to higher education institutions, which will lead to fundamentally positive changes in the higher education system. This, in turn, requires a new system-based approach to the management of family educational institutions. Assessment is an important part of the educational process. Constantly monitoring the quality of education

and students' knowledge levels is the basis for introducing important innovations into the educational process. Today, based on the new system, various forms of assessment have been developed and are being presented to the educational process. One of these is formative assessment.

By assessment, we mean the process of comparing the child's current achievements (failures), previous achievements (failures), and the correlation of educational results with the norms established by the current educational standards. The process of creating assessment criteria and forms is done together with students, and we see this as a way to build children's values. A set of formal and informal assessment methods adopted by teachers in the teaching process is called "Formative assessment". It is part of the learning process led by teachers and aims to improve student understanding and skills by changing teaching and learning methods.

MAIN PART

In this article, I will present several examples of specific subjects on the topic "Design-Based Assessment Methodology for Senior High School Students." It provides examples of a common method used to determine how to design learning and what parts of implementation in student assessment. We focus on this methodology to be more effective in assessing students by taking several examples from each subject, finding and analyzing them in general.

1. Mathematics: Equations and Graphing Lines

- The student designs a single algebraic equation or linear function.
- It graphs this function and explains its unique properties.
- Students will learn how to interpret a function and linear functions by analyzing graphs.

2. English: Novel Analysis and Details

- Students choose a novel or story and make a project about its characters, problems and events.

- When drafting, they fully absorb the analysis and details of the novel and express their opinions based on this.

3. Physics: Sohar's Analysis of Cells and Forces

- Students will take one selected from a series of samples and design it for analysis.

- They explain how cells and forces work and how they interact.

4. History: Foreign Cooperation Between States

- Students learn how a country should be able to cooperate in its foreign policy.

- When designing, they will analyze the historical cooperation of their chosen countries and establish what important economic, political and cultural connections they have.

5. Biology: Ecological Problems and Circles

- Students will design relationships between several biological problems and environmental problems.

- They express their suggestions, opinions and scientific reasons to solve these problems.

These examples are intended to demonstrate a more proactive approach to designing and assessing students in each subject to help them express themselves and apply what they have learned.

As an example of specific sciences, let's analyze the methodology of a particular subject. For example, consider taking mathematics:

1. Assessing Students' Conceptual Skills: Students will be able to answer questions about their mathematical concepts and skills. This is important to determine their level of understanding of the concepts.

2. Hands-on Activities and Projects: Hands-on activities and projects are effective for students to learn math skills. This gives them the opportunity to experience the practical application of mathematics and connect concepts with

practice.

3. Science Tests and Assessments: It is very important for students to assess their subjects through quizzes, quizzes and tests. This helps determine how they develop their math skills, how they solve problems, and how they learn new material.

4. Interactive Textbooks and Online Resources: Interactive textbooks and online resources that can be accessed via the Internet play a role in improving students' math skills.

5. Reviews and Discussions: Teachers need to analyze students as individuals, interact with them, and use reviews to better understand their approaches to learning mathematics.

6. Skill Sharing and Sharing: It is important to provide opportunities for students to express their independent opinions and share with others when learning math skills.

7. Class Period: Students should have appropriate class period to improve their mathematics knowledge. Each science period should help allocate enough time to study new material.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it can be said that it is necessary to pay attention to a number of essences related to the knowledge and use by other administrators of the methods used in the assessment of high school students. These methods strengthen the knowledge and skills of students and can be based on their ability to express their opinions, evaluate educational services, learn new knowledge, analyze and some other skills.

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